

FRACTURE AND FATIGUE OF PARTICULATE REINFORCED SILICON CARBIDE

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ABSTRACT

The fracture toughness of sintered silicon carbide (SiC) and silicon carbide reinforced with 16 volume % particulate titanium diboride (SiC/TiB₂) has been evaluated using precracked specimens in bending at temperatures of up to 1600°C in vacuum. A significant increase in toughness is observed in the composite material at ambient temperature, but not at 1200 and 1600°C in vacuum. The predominant toughening mechanism has been deduced to derive from a favourable distribution of thermal residual stresses formed on cooling from the sintering temperature.

No fatigue crack growth has been observed under cyclic loading in the monolithic silicon carbide. However, the composite material has been shown to be susceptible to cyclic fatigue at ambient temperature in air. Possible mechanisms of crack growth in the composite material are discussed.

Keywords: Silicon carbide, titanium diboride, composites, fracture, toughening, fatigue.

1. INTRODUCTION

The addition of a particulate phase to a ceramic matrix can toughen the matrix, for example TiB₂ particles in SiC (1, 2). Increased crack resistance may occur through the presence of thermal residual stresses caused by the coefficient of thermal expansion of the particles being greater than that of the matrix (3, 4). The residual compressive stress in the matrix, which forms as the composite is cooled from the sintering temperature of greater than 2000°C, has been postulated to reduce the effective stress intensity factor, K , as the crack is forced to propagate through regions under compression (3). Other mechanisms that may operate as a result of the addition of a particulate reinforcement include crack deflection around particles (5) and microcracking (4, 6). In considering these different mechanisms it is important to understand that their respective contributions to the overall toughness are not necessarily independent. For instance, the presence of thermal residual stresses may cause microcracks to develop near the crack tip as a small load is applied. This would locally relieve residual stresses and thus reduce the direct contribution to the toughness from these stresses, but the toughness could plausibly be increased, not only if these microcracks can shield the main crack, but also possibly due to preferential crack deflection towards microcracked regions.

In the present work, the toughening mechanisms in SiC/TiB₂ have been studied by a systematic comparison of the toughness of the matrix material with that of the composite material over a range of test temperatures. The useful upper temperature limit for use of SiC/TiB₂ in air is 1200°C because of oxidation of the TiB₂ particles (2). However, the possibility of testing at higher temperatures in vacuum (at up to 1600°C) means that the toughening mechanisms operating in the particulate reinforced composite can be investigated over a wider temperature range and potential effects of oxidation can be eliminated.

In addition, this paper addresses the resistance of these materials to crack growth under cyclic loading. Recently there has been a large amount of evidence to show that a wide range of ceramics and ceramic matrix composites are susceptible to cyclic (mechanical) fatigue and that these effects are additional to those observed from static and environmental contributions. In silicon carbide ceramics it has previously been observed that crack growth under cyclic loading only occurs in those materials which fail in an intergranular manner (7). Little crack growth data is available for ceramic materials subjected to static or cyclic loading. This may be due to experimental difficulties in attempting to initiate and grow a sub-critical crack in a brittle material. The bridge indentation method of precracking ceramics (8) has facilitated tests on specimens containing through-thickness precracks in this present study.

2. EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

2.1. Material

The materials tested were sintered monolithic SiC, and SiC containing 16% by volume particulate TiB₂, both supplied by Carborundum Co. (Niagara Falls, NY) and available commercially. The specimens were rectangular section polished bars and were tested in three and four point bending using an Instron 8501 series servohydraulic testing machine equipped with a 10 kN load cell.

2.2. Fracture Toughness Evaluation

SiC specimens measuring 6 x 6 x 50 mm and SiC/TiB₂ specimens measuring 8 x 4 x 50 mm had precracks introduced into them using the bridge indentation method (8). A Vickers hardness indentation was first made in the centre of the tensile surface of each specimen using a 10 kg applied load. The specimen was then loaded between two anvils using the fixtures shown schematically in Figure 1 with the indentation located above the centre of the 3 mm groove in the lower fixture. The centrality of the indentation and the alignment of the fixtures are of particular importance in the production of straight precracks in the mode I direction. A compressive load was applied to the specimen at a nominal displacement rate of 100 µm/minute using an ESH servohydraulic testing machine of 250 kN capacity. The load was removed as soon as a "pop-in" was heard. This indicated the initiation of the crack, usually at loads between 25 and 35 kN.

The crack length was measured optically and used to calculate the compliance, Y, from standard compliance tables (9). The specimens were then tested in four point bending and the failure load, P_{max}, was noted. The fracture toughness, K_{IC}, was then calculated using equations of the type:

$$K_{IC} = \frac{P_{max} Y}{B\sqrt{W}} \quad (1)$$

Three specimens of each material were tested under the following conditions: ambient temperature in air, and at the test temperatures of 1200 and 1600°C in vacuum.

2.3. Fatigue Crack Growth

Precracks were introduced into the specimens using the technique described in section 2.2. The lengths of both sides of the cracks were measured optically on the polished surfaces. Two fatigue tests on the composite material are reported here. All were conducted in bending at ambient temperature in air. An R ratio of 0.5 (where R = P_{min}/P_{max} and P_{min} and P_{max} are the minimum and maximum loads applied over the fatigue cycle respectively), and a frequency of 25 Hz were used. Typical initial K_{max} values were chosen to be 50% of the K_{IC} value. During testing P_{max} was increased incrementally while maintaining a constant R ratio.

The crack length was monitored by interrupting the test periodically and measuring the crack size optically. In one test on the composite material, the static load applied prior to cyclic loading was the same as the P_{max} of the loading cycle, shown schematically in Figure 2a. During the second test on SiC/16 vol.% TiB₂, the static hold was 20 N greater than the P_{max} applied during subsequent cyclic loading, Figure 2b. The static load was always applied for at least 40 000 seconds (the period

required to apply 10^6 cycles at 25 Hz). This was followed by a period of cyclic loading for at least 250 000 cycles. The monotonic and cyclic loading sequence was then repeated only if no crack growth had been observed during the previous 250 000 cycles.

2.4. Fractography

Scanning electron microscopy was carried out using an ISI 100A microscope at an accelerating voltage of 20 kV. Careful fractographic examination, including observations of opposite halves of matching fracture surfaces, of the composite material was undertaken in order to identify micromechanisms of crack extension.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Fracture Toughness

The results of the fracture toughness tests are shown in Figure 3. At ambient temperature a significant difference in toughness between the two materials is observed. However, this toughening as a result of the particulate reinforcement is reduced at elevated temperatures and at 1600°C the toughness of the two materials is essentially identical. A slight rise in toughness is observed as the test temperature is increased from 1200°C to 1600°C in both materials.

Figures 4 and 5 show matching halves of the transgranular fracture surfaces produced by testing SiC/16 vol.% TiB₂ at room temperature in air and at 1600°C in vacuum respectively. It can be seen that in the majority of cases the TiB₂ particles have decohered, resulting in crack deflection around the particles. Occasionally, particles crack and are visible on both fracture surfaces.

3.2. Fatigue Crack Growth

No subcritical crack growth under cyclic loading was observed in the monolithic SiC. Table 1 below shows the cyclic loading schedule applied to this specimen, which broke under a monotonically applied K of only 0.25 MPa√m greater than the K_{max} applied previously during cyclic loading.

Table 1 Cyclic loading conditions applied to precracked monolithic silicon carbide specimens tested in bending

P_{max}, N ($K_{max}, MPa\sqrt{m}$)	No. cycles survived
270 (1.54)	1 000 000
310 (1.77)	1 000 000
350 (2.00)	1 000 000
390 (2.22)	1 000 000
430 (2.45)	1 000 000
450 (2.57)	1 000 000
494 (2.82)	Failure under initial monotonic loading

Crack growth data from the tests on SiC/16 vol.% TiB₂ specimens have been plotted as crack length against time or number of cycles as appropriate in Figures 6 and 7. Straight lines have been plotted between data points as an approximation to the crack growth behaviour. It can be seen that the

majority of crack growth occurred under cyclic loading. It is important to note that when a small amount of crack growth was observed under a static load, the crack arrested and did not extend again until a cyclic load was applied, even though the initial P_{\max} applied during the cyclic loading was less than that previously applied during the static hold.

Fracture surfaces from areas of the specimen which failed under cyclic loading and during final failure are shown in Figures 7 and 8 respectively. It appears that more particles of TiB_2 are present on the fracture surface from the fatigue region than from the final failure region. The failure path is transgranular in nature in regions of both subcritical crack growth and final failure.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Toughening Mechanisms in SiC/16 vol.% TiB_2

It has previously been suggested that local compressive stresses in the continuous matrix phase are the most important factor in promoting increased toughness in SiC/ TiB_2 particulate reinforced composites compared with monolithic SiC (3, 4). These residual stresses must derive from such factors as the effective modulus, thermal expansion mismatch and the temperature range over which these stresses are formed. It therefore follows that the mechanism of toughening will be less potent at elevated temperatures, since the material may plausibly be assumed to be stress free at the processing (sintering) temperature of greater than 2000°C. Unless the particle/matrix interface strength changes over the temperature range under consideration, the results of the present study lend strong support to this general mechanism, since the improvement in toughness of the composite material over the matrix decreases as the temperature is increased. (It is difficult to envisage major changes to interfacial strength at test temperatures of 1600°C in vacuum, as prior sintering was performed at higher temperatures. Moreover, fractographic observations, Figures 4 and 5, suggest that the majority of particles decohere at all test temperatures.)

Previous work (10) has indicated that only at ambient temperature is there any indication that additional toughening mechanisms are required to explain the improved toughness of the composite. Other potential sources of toughening in this particular system are crack deflection, twisting and tilting of the crack front, and microcracking. Fractography indicates that the majority of TiB_2 particles decohere in the composite material at all temperatures considered here. Such observations suggest that relatively weak interfacial bonding exists between the SiC matrix and TiB_2 particles. However, crack deflection around the particles must make an insignificant contribution to the toughness of the composite because, while such deflection has been observed at all test temperatures, the toughness of the composite markedly exceeds that of the monolithic material at ambient temperature only. Other additional contributions to toughness from particulate reinforcement potentially come from matrix grain size reduction; additional crack front pinning, bowing and branching. As all such effects are likely to be largely temperature independent, then they must also be insignificant in the present system because they do not appear to promote the toughness of the composite material above that of the monolithic material at elevated temperatures. It is therefore deduced that the toughening observed derives principally from a favourable residual stress distribution generated by the thermal expansion mismatch between the SiC matrix and TiB_2 particles. Modelling studies also support this deduction (3, 12).

It has previously been shown that the fracture surface of the composite material is significantly rougher than that of the monolithic material at ambient temperature only (10). It therefore appears that there is some preferential crack deflection towards certain TiB_2 particles or clusters of particles at room temperature and this may also be a contributory factor in the overall toughening mechanism. This crack deflection is likely to be a result of prior microcracking of the particles and/or redistribution of residual stresses in the particles and matrix before the onset of catastrophic failure.

4.2. Fatigue Crack Growth Mechanisms

Fatigue crack growth has been observed in the composite material only. Other work (11) has shown that subcritical crack growth appears to occur in bursts, which may indicate that damage accumulation processes are important. If the TiB_2 particles and interfaces were damaged ahead of

the crack tip during cyclic loading, the benign compressive stresses which toughen the matrix would be partially relieved and then local crack extension may plausibly occur. A mechanism for crack arrest is then required to prevent catastrophic failure with crack extension. If TiB₂ particles are dislodged during crack advance, then they would be expected to cause crack closure by wedging of the crack surfaces. Fractographic observations have been unable to support this mechanism fully at the present time and further work is still required to substantiate it.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The fracture toughness of monolithic SiC and SiC/16 vol.% TiB₂ particulate reinforced composites has been evaluated at ambient temperature, and at 1200 and 1600°C in vacuum using precracked specimens in bending. A significant increase in toughness is observed for the composite material at ambient temperature and this difference decreases as the test temperature is increased. The predominant toughening mechanism of the composite material is deduced to result from a favourable distribution of thermal residual stresses. Fractographic observations suggest that the bonding between the SiC and TiB₂ particulate is relatively weak because interfacial decohesion of particles is observed at all test temperatures.

Sintered SiC/16 vol.% TiB₂ has been shown to be susceptible to cyclic fatigue. This is not due to static effects, since crack growth occurs at lower values of K_{max} under subsequent cyclic loading than that applied previously under static loading. Fatigue crack growth is deduced to occur by prior damage to TiB₂ particles, followed by local crack extension through the SiC matrix.

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References

- 1 McMurty, C.H., Boecker, D.G., Seshadri, S.S., Zanghi, J. S. and Garnier, J.E., *Microstructure and Material Properties of SiC/TiB₂ Composites*, Am. Ceram. Soc. Bull., Vol. 66, No. 2, 1987, pp. 325-329
- 2 Janney, M.A., *Mechanical Properties and Oxidation Behaviour of a Hot-Pressed SiC-15-vol%-TiB₂ Composite*, Am. Ceram. Soc. Bull., Vol. 66, No. 2, 1987, pp. 322 - 324
- 3 Taya, M., Hayashi, S., Kobayashi, A.W. and Yoon, H.S., *Toughening of a particulate reinforced ceramic matrix composite by thermal residual stresses*, J. Am. Ceram. Soc., Vol. 73, No. 5, 1990, pp. 1382 - 1391
- 4 Magley, D.J., Winholtz, R.A. and Faber, K.T., *Residual Stresses in a Two-Phase Microcracking Ceramic*, J. Am. Ceram. Soc., Vol. 73, No. 6, 1990, pp. 1641 - 1644
- 5 Seshadri, S.G., Srinivasan, M. and Keeler, K.M., *Numerical Computation of the Toughening Increments Due to Crack Deflection in Particulate Composites*, Ceram. Eng. Sci. Proc., Vol. 8, No. 7 - 8, 1987, pp. 671-684
- 6 Gu, W.-H., Faber, K.T. and Steinbrech, R.W., *Microcracking and R-Curve Behaviour in SiC-TiB₂ Composites*, Acta Metall. Mater., Vol. 40, No. 11, 1992, pp. 3121 - 3128
- 7 Horibe, S. and Hirahara, R., *Cyclic Fatigue of Ceramic Materials: Influence of Crack Path and Fatigue Mechanisms*, Acta Metall. Mater., Vol. 39, No. 6, 1991, pp. 1309 - 1317
- 8 Nose, T. and Fujii, T., *Evaluation of Fracture Toughness for Ceramic Materials by a Single-Edge Precracked-Beam Method*, J. Amer. Ceram. Soc., Vol. 71, No. 5, 1988, pp. 328 - 333
- 9 Srawley, J.E. and Gross, B. in *Side-Cracked Plates Subjected to Combined Direct and Bending Forced, Cracks and Fracture*, ASTM STP 601, 1976, pp. 559 - 579
- 10 Brett, R.L. and Bowen, P., *Micromechanisms of Toughening in a Particulate Reinforced Ceramic Matrix Composite*, Ceram. Eng and Sci. Proc., Vol. 13, No. 7 - 8, 1992, pp. 99 - 106
- 11 Brett, R.L. and Bowen, P., *Cyclic Fatigue in a SiC-Based Ceramic Matrix Composite*, Proc. Conf. "Fatigue 93", Montreal, Canada, May 1993
- 12 Brett, R.L., *Fracture and Fatigue of SiC-Based Ceramics*, PhD Thesis, The University of Birmingham, 1993

Figure 1 Schematic diagram of the fixtures used to precrack ceramic specimens

Figure 2 Schematic diagrams of loading schedules applied to specimens when the static hold is (a) equal to and (b) greater than the maximum load subsequently applied during cyclic loading

Figure 3 Effect of temperature on the fracture toughness of sintered SiC and SiC/16 vol.% TiB₂

Figure 4 Matching halves of the fracture surfaces of SiC/16 vol.% TiB₂ produced at ambient temperature in air. Equivalent areas of interest are marked.

Figure 5 Matching halves of the fracture surfaces of SiC/16 vol.% TiB₂ produced at 1600°C in vacuum. Equivalent areas of interest are marked.

Figure 6 Crack growth in SiC/16 vol.% TiB₂ at ambient temperature. Loading schedule shown.

Figure 7 Crack growth in SiC/16 vol.% TiB₂ at ambient temperature. Loading schedule shown.

Figure 8 Fatigue surface produced at ambient temperature in SiC/16 vol.% TiB₂

Figure 9 Region of final failure - same specimen as Figure 8